

Factors Influencing Consumers' Intention to Avoid Fast Fashion: A Comparative Study of Milan and Shanghai

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Abstract

The fast fashion industry contributes significantly to environmental degradation, contributing to primary microplastics entering water bodies through synthetic fiber shedding. Understanding consumer intentions to avoid fast fashion requires examining both psychological and cultural determinants. This study explores the factors of consumers' behavioral intentions to avoid plastic-based fast fashion garments in Milan, Italy (n=151) and Shanghai, China (n=148). Employing an extended Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) framework that includes environmental concern and biospheric values as antecedents, we investigated how attitude, subjective norms, environmental concern, and biospheric values influence avoidance intentions. Structural equation modeling revealed that all hypothesized relationships were significant in both cultural contexts, with the model explaining 57.9% of the variance in Milan and 76.8% in Shanghai. Notably, the effect of attitude on behavioral intention was stronger in Shanghai ($\beta=0.598$) compared to Milan ($\beta=0.494$), while biospheric values more strongly predicted environmental concern in Milan ($\beta=0.433$) in contrast to Shanghai ($\beta=0.291$). The key innovation of this study lies in its comparison of attitudes toward microplastic effects from fast fashion across cultures, revealing that while universal psychological mechanisms drive sustainable consumption intentions, cultural contexts shape the relative strength of value-based versus attitude-based pathways. These findings suggest that interventions to reduce fast fashion consumption should be culturally tailored, focusing on personal attitudes in collectivistic contexts and value-based environmental education in individualistic settings.

Keywords: *Fast fashion avoidance, microplastic pollution, Theory of Reasoned Action, sustainable consumption, cross-cultural consumer behavior.*

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Introduction

Humanity must address the environmental consequences of consumption to stay within planetary boundaries, as issues like climate change, biodiversity loss, ecological degradation, and pollution continue to escalate (Steffen et al., 2015). The clothing industry is a clear example of this challenge, as its environmental impact has intensified significantly in recent decades (United Nations Climate Change, 2018). The fast fashion business model, characterized by rapid production and consumption of inexpensive, trendy clothing, relies on short product life cycles driven by consumer demand for novel and affordable items. This model has increased textile production and consumption volumes, creating a culture of frequent purchases and disposability (Sagapova et al., 2022; Sahimaa et al., 2023).

The environmental impact of fast fashion is significant and multifaceted, with a particularly alarming contribution to microplastic pollution. Fast fashion accounts for approximately 35% of primary microplastics that end up in water bodies, mainly from synthetic fibers such as polyester (Niinimäki et al., 2020). The industry relies on cheap synthetic materials derived from fossil fuels, which amplifies its environmental footprint. Polyester, the dominant fiber in the industry, has a high carbon footprint during production and releases microplastics during washing, polluting aquatic ecosystems and entering the food chain (Jorige & Satani, 2024).

Microplastics, plastic particles smaller than 5mm (Zou et al., 2021), have become one of the main environmental challenges associated with fast fashion. Global synthetic fiber production has surged dramatically, increasing from 57 million metric tons (MMT) in 2000 to 111 MMT in 2020, with projections estimating 145 MMT by 2030, accounting for 65% of worldwide textile production (Periyasamy & Tehrani-Bagha, 2022). Synthetic textiles shed microfibers during wash and dry cycles, contributing substantially to microplastic pollution and directly linking apparel choices to environmental pollution pathways (Jorige & Satani, 2024).

Empirical evidence confirms the widespread presence of microplastics originating from textiles in water bodies (De Falco et al., 2019; Hernandez et al., 2017). In the Ciwalengke River, Indonesia, microplastic distribution was dominated by fiber particles (polyester and nylon) primarily derived from residents' clothing and textile industry washing processes (Alam et al., 2019). In Malaysia, analysis of 99 samples of domestic wash water detected the presence of microplastics consisting mainly of polyester, nylon, and acrylic fibers, highlighting the contribution of domestic washing machines to microplastic pollution (Praveena et al., 2021). Laboratory studies also confirm that acrylic, nylon, and polyester fabrics shed fibers during washing (Carney Almroth et al., 2018).

Despite growing attention to this problem, the absence of regulations or measurement standards for microplastics in textiles (Sigaard & Laitala, 2023) makes consumer behavior change a critical pathway for addressing this environmental challenge. The clothing sector is responsible for excessive consumption (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2017), and reducing clothing purchases by extending the life of garments can significantly mitigate the ecological impacts of the textile industry (Niinimäki et al., 2020). Technical solutions alone are not enough to adequately address the negative effects of the growing textile industry, as increasing levels of production and consumption compromise technological advancements. Improvements in resource efficiency must be accompanied by changes in consumption patterns and a reduction in the use of materials (Sigaard & Laitala, 2023). As a result of this urgency, global discussions now prioritize environmental issues (Sreen et al., 2018), with "Responsible consumption and production" and "Sustainable cities and communities" incorporated into the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (United Nations, 2015).

However, while the technical and environmental aspects of microplastic pollution caused by fast fashion are increasingly well documented, the psychological and cultural factors influencing consumers' willingness to avoid synthetic fast fashion garments remain largely unexplored. Most existing research on sustainable consumption in the fashion industry has focused generally on environmental attitudes without specifically examining consumer responses to microplastic pollution, which is one of the most significant but least visible environmental impacts of fast fashion. Furthermore, although cultural factors have been shown to significantly influence environmental attitudes and behaviors, few studies have examined how these psychological mechanisms operate in different cultural contexts. Understanding these intercultural differences is essential for developing effective and culturally appropriate interventions aimed at promoting sustainable consumption behaviors. This study fills this gap by investigating the determinants of consumers' intention to avoid fast-fashion clothing made from plastic in two culturally distinct contexts: Milan, Italy, and Shanghai, China.

Theoretical Framework: Theory of Reasoned Action

The theory of reasoned action (TRA) posits that behavioral intentions, influenced by attitudes and subjective norms, are the main predictors of behavior (Ajzen, 1980). This framework has been successful in understanding green purchase behaviors (Ha & Janda, 2012) and sustainable consumption practices (Davies et al., 2002).

Although the Theory of Planned Behavior extends TRA by incorporating perceived behavioral control, TRA is still suitable for this study since fast fashion avoidance involves primarily voluntary behavior where consumers have direct purchasing control (Chen, 2022).

Recent research validates TRA in sustainable apparel contexts, highlighting the significant impact of attitude and normative factors strongly on intentions (Liaquat et al., 2024; Yadav et al., 2022). Attitude, TRA's central element and the only construct we have expanded, consistently predicts environmental behavioral intentions (Bassi, 2023; Pérez et al., 2021).

Environmental concern (EC), defined as "the degree to which people are aware of environmental problems and support efforts to solve them" (Dunlap & Jones, 2002), acts as a significant antecedent in TRA models. Studies demonstrate that EC positively affects attitudes toward green products (Hartmann & Apaolaza-Ibañez, 2012; Paul et al., 2016), with attitude acting as a mediator in the relationship between EC and purchase intention (Andika et al., 2024).

Building on value-belief-norm theory (Stern, 1999), this research integrates biospheric values as determinants of environmental concern. The three-value framework (egoistic, altruistic, biospheric) established by de Groot and Steg (2007, 2008) shows that biospheric values account for about 30% of the variance in environmental concerns and strongly influence pro-environmental behavior (van der Werff et al., 2013). Self-transcendence values, including biospheric concern, positively affect attitudes toward sustainable clothing (Jacobs et al., 2018).

By extending the Theory of Reasoned Action with environmental concern and biospheric values, and comparing these psychological pathways across Western European individualistic culture and East Asian collectivistic culture, this research provides novel insights into how cultural contexts shape the relationship between environmental values, microplastic awareness, and sustainable consumption intentions.

Methodology

This research follows a three-step approach: first, we develop research hypotheses based on an extended TRA model; next, we design a questionnaire and conduct surveys in Shanghai and Milan to collect our data; finally, we analyze the data using structural equation modeling (SEM), specifically focusing on the partial least squares (PLS) method.

Research Hypothesis

Based on the literature of Section 2, the hypotheses are presented, which are: attitude (ATT) positively affects consumers' behavioral intention (BI) of sustainable consumption, avoiding fast fashion plastic-made items in Milan and Shanghai (H1); subjective norms (SN) positively affect consumers' behavioral intention (BI) of sustainable consumption, avoiding fast fashion plastic-made items in Milan and Shanghai (H2); environmental concern (EC) positively affects ATT (H3); biospheric values (BV) positively affects EC (H4) (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Research Model

Questionnaire Design

The questionnaire is divided into two main sections. The first section focuses on gathering demographic information such as participants' gender, age, educational background, and income levels. In the second section, we explore the measurement variables that align with our research model and hypotheses. The questions designed to assess each factor are adapted from the fundamental studies (de Groot & Steg, 2007, 2008; Dunlap et al., 2000; Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975; Steg et al., 2014; Stern et al., 1998) and previous ones (see Table 1), adopting a seven-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (“strongly disagree”) to 7 (“strongly agree”). A pilot survey was implemented and met the reliability requirement.

Table 1. Literature for Measurement Adaptation

Constructs	Items	Literature source
Attitude (ATT)	3	(Jacobs et al., 2018)
Subjective Norms (SN)	3	(Silva et al., 2021)
Environmental Concern (EN)	3	(Jacobs et al., 2018)
Biospheric Values (BV)	2	(Batool et al., 2023; Tolppanen & Kang, 2021)
Behavioral Intention (BI)	4	(Yoon et al., 2020)

Data Collection

Data collection was done in two stages. To gather data for the Italian sample, we conducted online research. A questionnaire was created using Google Forms and shared on social media platforms such as Instagram, LinkedIn, Facebook, and WhatsApp. Some Italian university professors were contacted, asking them to distribute the link to their students. This approach utilized snowball sampling to reach more participants. For the Chinese sample, data were collected in person over two weeks. The researchers visited busy shopping malls in Shanghai's Yangpu District and randomly approached people to participate, using a convenience sampling method in a public setting. 183 samples were collected from Milan and 180 from Shanghai. Before analysis, a common approach was implemented to identifying inconsistent responses, in order to look for participants who show little variation in their responses. To quantify this, the standard deviation of each respondent's responses was calculated, in line with recommendations in the methodological literature (Huang et al., 2012). Responses with a standard deviation below a threshold of 0.25 were removed from the dataset. This cleaning procedure resulted in the removal of 32 responses from the Italian sample and 32 from the Chinese sample, leaving a final analytic sample of n = 151 and n = 148, respectively (see Table 2).

Table 2. Demographic Data of the Survey Sample

Characteristic	Milan (n=151)		Shanghai (n=148)	
	number	percent	number	percent
Gender				
Female	103	68.2%	106	71.6%
Male	47	31.1%	39	26.4%
Prefer not to say	1	0.7%	3	2.0%
Age				
<25	62	41.1%	102	68.9%
26-46	62	41.1%	32	21.6%
47-67	25	16.6%	13	8.8%
>67	2	1.3%	1	0.7%
Educational level				
Up to high school	40	26.5%	9	6.1%
Undergraduate	62	41.1%	87	58.8%
Postgraduate	49	32.5%	52	35.1%
Income level (monthly)*				
1	67	44.4%	76	51.4%
2	59	39.1%	44	29.7%
3	6	4.0%	19	12.8%
4	3	2.0%	9	6.1%
5	16	10.6%	0	0.0%

Note: *(Milan: 1: <1,000€; 2: 1,000 – 2,999€; 3: 3,000 – 4,999€; 4: > 5,000€; 5: Prefer not to say; Shanghai: 1: < 3,000¥; 2: 3,000 – 10,000¥; 3: 10,000 – 20,000¥; 4: > 20,000¥; 5: Prefer not to say.)

The final sample sizes of 151 (Milan) and 148 (Shanghai) are methodologically adequate for this study for several reasons. First, these sample sizes are consistent with the guidelines established for research in the behavioral and social sciences that uses structural equation modeling. (Hair et al., 2019) suggest that for PLS-SEM, a minimum sample size can be calculated as ten times the largest number of structural paths directed at a particular construct in the structural model. In our model, the maximum number of paths directed at any construct is two, suggesting a minimum sample of 20 per group; our samples exceed this threshold substantially.

Second, published research on sustainable fashion consumption using similar theoretical frameworks and analytical approaches demonstrates that sample sizes in the range of 100-200 respondents per subgroup are adequate and commonly accepted. Floriano & Matos (2022) successfully examined sustainable fashion intentions among Brazilian consumers with n=179, while Kurniaty et al. (2024) investigated sustainable fashion consumption among Indonesian consumers with n=155.

Finally, the bootstrapping procedure employed in PLS-SEM (with 5,000 resamples in this study) provides robust standard error estimates and significance tests even with moderate sample sizes, as it does not rely on large-sample asymptotic assumptions (Hair et al., 2021). The path coefficients reported in our analysis, as well as the adequate model fit indices, provide empirical evidence that our sample sizes were sufficient to test the hypothesized effects.

Data Analysis

The study aims to examine whether and how the factors of ATT, SN, EC, and BV affect the behavioral intention of consumers in Milan and Shanghai to engage in sustainable fashion consumption, which has the avoidance of fast fashion as a central component.

Results

Measurement Model

The measurement model is tested by convergent validity and discriminant validity. Convergent validity shows how strongly related similar constructs are, indicating that they have a strong connection. This aspect is typically assessed using the loading, composite reliability (CR), and the average variance extracted (AVE) of each indicator item. Each loading figure has to be above 0.7 (Hair et al., 2019). When the Composite Reliability (CR) exceeds 0.7, the group of indicators demonstrates internal consistency. An Average Variance Extracted (AVE) greater than 0.5 indicates reliability. In our results, all variables show a CR above 0.7 and an AVE above 0.5, except for the variable EC in the sample of Shanghai, which is slightly below the threshold (see Table 3). Since its CR is above 0.6, the AVE value can be accepted.

Table 3. Composite reliability and AVE (Average Variance Extracted)

Construct/Group	Milan	Shanghai
Composite reliability (CR>0.7)		
ATT	0.786	0.857
SN	0.922	0.892
BV	0.827	0.851
EC	0.799	0.767
BI	0.916	0.893
Average Variance Extracted (AVE>0.5)		
ATT	0.525	0.667
SN	0.765	0.724
BV	0.673	0.74
EC	0.561	0.496
BI	0.722	0.671

Two methods are used to assess discriminant validity: the method developed by Fornell & Larcker (1981) suggests that the square root of the AVE for each construct needs to be higher than the squared shared variance with other variables, and the test using the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT), whose value must be below 0.9 to support discriminant validity. When evaluating both methods, our data showed satisfactory values for discriminant validity (see Tables 4 & 5).

Table 4. Fornell & Larcker Criterion Results

	ATT		BV		EC		INT		SN	
	Shanghai	Milan								
ATT	0.817	0.725								
BV	0.342	0.466	0.86	0.82						
EC	0.658	0.706	0.36	0.533	0.704	0.749				
BI	0.871	0.739	0.353	0.42	0.528	0.57	0.819	0.85		
SN	0.761	0.554	0.396	0.254	0.508	0.395	0.723	0.561	0.851	0.874

Table 5. Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) Results

	ATT		BV		EC		INT		SN	
	Shanghai	Milan								
ATT										
BV	0.342	0.468								
EC	0.655	0.709	0.333	0.54						
BI	0.872	0.723	0.353	0.419	0.515	0.576				
SN	0.76	0.538	0.397	0.251	0.488	0.403	0.72	0.561		

Structure Model and Hypothesis Testing

After validating the measurement model, the model's explanatory strength was illustrated using the coefficient of determination (R^2) for the endogenous variables. A minimum R^2 value of 0.02 is required to indicate a good fit (Hair et al., 2021). The results (see Table 6) indicate that the model possesses substantial explanatory power for both cultural contexts.

Table 6. R^2 Results

	Group	R^2
BI	Milan	0.579
	Shanghai	0.768
ATT	Milan	0.499
	Shanghai	0.433
EC	Milan	0.284
	Shanghai	0.13

To evaluate all the hypotheses for both the Milan and Shanghai samples, a structural equation model was developed in SmartPLS4, and a Bootstrap Test was performed using 5000 subsamples via resampling. The path coefficients (β), standard errors, and results of the hypothesis testing are shown in Table 7. The analysis finds strong support for all proposed relationships in both cultural settings. For the Milan sample, all four hypotheses were supported ($p < 0.001$). Attitude (ATT) proved to have a significant influence on behavioral intention ($\beta = 0.494$), while subjective norms (SN) showed a moderate effect ($\beta = 0.283$). The relationship between biospheric values and environmental concern was confirmed ($\beta = 0.433$), and environmental concern strongly predicted attitudes ($\beta = 0.560$). Similarly, for the Shanghai sample, strong support was found for all hypotheses ($p < 0.001$). In particular, attitude showed an even stronger effect on behavioral intentions ($\beta = 0.598$) than in the Milan sample. Subjective norms maintained a significant though slightly weaker influence ($\beta = 0.247$), while the path from biospheric values to environmental concern was significant but comparatively weaker ($\beta = 0.291$) than in Milan.

Table 7. Hypothesis Testing of Shanghai and Mumbai (Bootstrapping = 5000)

Hypothesis	Milan		Shanghai	
	Path Coefficients (β)	Findings	Path Coefficients (β)	Findings
H1 ATT → BI	0.494*** (0.062)	Supported	0.598*** (0.076)	Supported
H2 SN → BI	0.283*** (0.075)	Supported	0.247*** (0.072)	Supported
H3 EC → ATT	0.560*** (0.085)	Supported	0.533*** (0.069)	Supported
H4 BV → EC	0.433*** (0.104)	Supported	0.291*** (0.061)	Supported

Note: *** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$.

All the hypotheses tested were significant in both cultural contexts, demonstrating the model's cross-cultural validity. The link between attitude and intention (H1) was stronger in Shanghai ($\beta = 0.598$) than in Milan ($\beta = 0.494$). The relationship between biospheric values and environmental concern (H4) was more evident in Milan ($\beta = 0.433$) than in Shanghai ($\beta = 0.291$). Finally, the environmental concern-attitude pathway showed consistency across cultures ($\beta = 0.560$ vs $\beta = 0.533$) (see Figures 2 & 3).

Figure 2. Hypothesis Testing of the Milan Sample

Figure 3. Hypothesis Testing of the Shanghai Sample

Discussion

This study investigated determinants of consumers' intention to avoid fast-fashion plastic-made garments in Milan, Italy, and Shanghai, China. By extending the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) with environmental concern (EC) and biospheric values (BV), the model demonstrated strong explanatory power, accounting for 57.9% of variance in behavioral intention (BI) in Milan and 76.8% in Shanghai. The study innovatively compares attitudes towards the effect of microplastics resulting from fast fashion across different cultures, demonstrating that while universal psychological mechanisms influence

sustainable consumption intentions, cultural contexts affect the strength of value-based versus attitude-based pathways. All four hypotheses (H1-H4) were confirmed in both contexts, validating the extended TRA model.

The strong, positive relationship between attitude and behavioral intention ($\beta_{\text{Milan}} = 0.494$; $\beta_{\text{Shanghai}} = 0.598$) confirms that positive personal attitudes toward sustainable fashion powerfully drive intention to avoid fast fashion. This path was stronger in Shanghai, suggesting that for Chinese consumers, personal belief is key in shaping behavioral intentions. This is consistent with research conducted by Floriano and de Matos (2022) among Brazilian consumers, Kumar et al. (2022) among Indian youth, and Pérez et al. (2021) in apparel contexts. The stronger connection between attitude and intention in Shanghai may reflect the features of a collectivist culture, in which attitudes blend personal evaluation with societal expectations (Sreen et al., 2018). The younger demographic profile (68.9% under 25 years) demonstrates greater consistency between attitude and intention (Kumar et al., 2022), and additionally, the implementation of environmental awareness campaigns in urban China contributes to this phenomenon (Zhang & Huang, 2024). Practically, interventions in China should focus on shaping attitudes through persuasive messaging emphasizing microplastic pollution concerns.

Support for H2 ($\beta_{\text{Milan}} = 0.283$; $\beta_{\text{Shanghai}} = 0.247$) confirms that social pressure significantly influences intention in both individualistic and collectivistic cultures. This aligns with research across Asian, Middle Eastern, and European consumers (Armutcu et al., 2025), Generation Z Chinese consumers (Zhang & Huang, 2024), and second-hand clothing purchase intentions in China (Nawaz et al., 2022). Interestingly, contrary to cultural dimensions theory predictions, the influence of subjective norms appeared to be slightly stronger in Milan. This might be due to the enhanced public exposure of sustainable fashion in Milan, which is renowned as a global fashion hub, differences in methodology (in-person vs. online collection), or a generational shift towards individualism among urban Chinese youth (Kurniaty et al., 2024). The similar level of influence across cultures indicates that social influence mechanisms are universal. However, the sources vary: in Milan, fashion-conscious peers and media discourse, while in Shanghai, government campaigns and social media influencers in arise (Kurniaty et al., 2024). Social marketing campaigns should utilize normative messaging in both contexts, but tailor specific sources to fit the cultural context.

The link between biospheric values and environmental concern was significant. Yet, it was noticeably stronger in Milan ($\beta = 0.433$) compared to Shanghai ($\beta = 0.291$), suggesting that beliefs about nature's inherent value are a more powerful source of environmental concern for consumers in Italy. This is in line with Yang et al. (2024) on biospheric values in sustainable fashion consumption. The stronger Milan relationship may reflect Western European environmental education emphasizing intrinsic values (Bassi, 2023), greater age diversity with more crystallized value systems, and cultural differences where individualistic cultures prioritize abstract principles while collectivistic cultures emphasize practical considerations (Sreen et al., 2018). The weaker Shanghai relationship suggests biospheric values contribute to environmental concern, but through more complex mechanisms. Environmental education programs in Milan may be especially impactful when highlighting the inherent value of nature, while initiatives in Shanghai might be more effective when addressing immediate threats and practical solutions.

The path from environmental concern to attitude was consistently strong and almost identical across samples ($\beta_{\text{Milan}} = 0.560$; $\beta_{\text{Shanghai}} = 0.533$), indicating that once environmental concern is established, it leads to positive attitudes with notable cultural uniformity, confirming the findings of Adam et al. (2021) in Indonesia's textile industry and Pérez et al. (2021) on ethical fashion. This cross-cultural consistency suggests a universal psychological mechanism where awareness of environmental issues shapes sustainable consumption evaluations, validating TRA's theoretical extension with environmental concern (Andika et al., 2024). Educational campaigns that enhance microplastic pollution awareness should effectively shape positive attitudes across diverse cultural settings.

Shanghai's high R^2 (0.768) indicates a significant influence of attitudes on intentions among urban educated youth in China (Kurniaty et al., 2024; Zhang & Huang, 2024). Conversely, Milan's stronger value-concern relationship ($R^2 = 0.284$ for EC) reflects deeper foundation of environmentalism in this fashion capital (Bassi, 2023). These patterns imply that while TRA provides a valid cross-cultural foundation, psychological pathway importance varies systematically: collectivistic contexts show attitude-driven conversion of concern to intentions, while individualistic contexts show stronger value-concern links with more complex processes from concern to intention (Bassi, 2023; Sreen et al., 2018).

Conclusion

This study explores factors influencing consumers' intention to avoid fast fashion in Milan and Shanghai using an extended Theory of Reasoned Action incorporating environmental concern and biospheric values as attitude antecedents. While the overall framework applies in both cities, the relative strength of psychological pathways differs across cultures. All four hypothesized relationships were supported: attitude and subjective norms significantly predict behavioral intention, with attitude stronger in Shanghai and subjective norms comparable across contexts; environmental concern consistently predicts attitude in both cultures, while biospheric values more strongly predict environmental concern in Milan than in Shanghai.

This research presents several significant theoretical contributions. Firstly, it reaffirms the relevance of TRA for understanding sustainable consumption intentions, demonstrating that when extended with relevant antecedents, it effectively captures psychological processes with high explanatory power (57.9%-76.8% of variance in behavioral intention). Secondly, the integration of TRA with environmental concern and biospheric values creates a link to the Value-belief-norm Theory, thereby deepening the understanding of pro-environmental behavior. Thirdly, the cross-cultural comparison reveals that while the basic TRA framework is applicable worldwide, the significance of pathways differs across cultural contexts, contributing to the understanding of cross-cultural consumer behavior. Finally, focusing on microplastic pollution as a consequence of fast fashion advances sustainable fashion literature by highlighting how scientifically validated environmental threats significantly shape consumer attitudes and intentions.

The study's main contribution lies in its examination of attitudes towards the environmental effects of fast fashion across different cultures, highlighting that concerns about microplastics transcend cultural boundaries, even though their origins differ. This suggests that while universal psychological mechanisms can promote sustainable consumption, strategies must be adapted to specific cultural contexts. Few studies specifically address how consumers respond to microplastic-related issues. Our findings show that environmental concern about microplastics, when communicated effectively, shapes attitudes and intentions across cultures. This issue has a universal appeal, connecting personal consumption to documented environmental harm (Jorige & Satani, 2024). Given growing evidence of microplastic contamination in ecosystems and human health (Periyasamy & Tehrani-Bagha, 2022), educational initiatives illustrating how synthetic fabrics shed microfibers during washing can effectively promote sustainable consumption.

These findings have significant implications for policymakers, stakeholders in the fashion industry, and sustainability advocates. First, interventions should be culturally tailored: marketing in China should emphasize sustainable choice benefits, while European campaigns should highlight the intrinsic value of ecosystems. Second, the relationship between environmental concern and attitude highlights the importance of public education regarding microplastic pollution from fast fashion. Fashion brands, NGOs, and government agencies should collaborate to educate consumers about the impact of synthetic textiles and promote alternative materials. Third, social marketing approaches leveraging social proof and culturally relevant influencers can effectively encourage the avoidance of fast fashion. Fourth, industry stakeholders must acknowledge consumer environmental concerns and invest in sustainable materials

and technologies that minimize microfiber shedding. Finally, policymakers should consider regulations aimed at tackling microplastic pollution, such as synthetic content labeling requirements and standards for microfiber shedding, which are likely to receive consumer support in both cultural contexts.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the sample mainly includes young, educated urban residents, especially in Shanghai (68.9% under 25), which limits the ability to generalize findings to broader populations. Future research should investigate a range of demographics, such as those from rural areas and individuals with lower education levels. Second, the cross-sectional design measures intentions at a single time. Although intention is a predictor of behavior (Frommeyer et al., 2022), the intention-behavior gap is well-documented (Nguyen & Nguyen, 2017), which suggests that longitudinal studies are needed to assess sustained behavioral change. Third, different data collection methods (online in Milan, in-person in Shanghai) may have contributed to variability. Future cross-cultural research should maintain consistent methods. Fourth, additional factors like perceived behavioral control and knowledge about microplastics might also influence intentions. Fifth, a lower AVE for environmental concern in Shanghai (0.496) indicates potential difficulties in measurement that require for culturally tailored instruments. Finally, focusing only on Milan and Shanghai limits generalizability to Italy and China overall. Future studies should investigate patterns in additional cities and cultural settings globally.

Several research paths emerge: conducting longitudinal studies to confirm the conversion of intention into behavior; examination of different demographic groups; investigation of additional factors (perceived behavioral control, microplastic knowledge, fashion involvement, personal norms, and financial limitations); applying the model in various cultural contexts; performing intervention studies to evaluate the effectiveness of different campaign strategies; and assessing the entire sustainable fashion consumption lifecycle from awareness to disposal.

Addressing fast fashion requires culturally tailored strategies, as a universal solution is not effective for everyone. Given the industry's growth and its significant environmental impact, especially microplastic pollution, it is crucial to understand psychological and cultural factors influencing consumers' willingness to avoid fast fashion is crucial. Collaboration efforts among consumers, industry, policymakers, and civil society are essential for moving towards sustainable consumption habits. By recognizing cultural differences, stakeholders can create more impactful strategies promoting sustainable fashion and tackling urgent environmental challenges. As consumer environmental awareness increases, there is an opportunity to leverage this concern for meaningful behavioral change that can reduce the fashion industry's environmental footprint.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare there are no financial interests or personal relationships that may have impacted the work reported in this paper. All contributions were made exclusively in an academic and scientific context. The views and interpretations presented are entirely those of the authors, independent of any organizations that might benefit from this publication.

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